

Contagious of diseases epidemiological situation seeing exit

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By the beginning of the 21st century, medicine has achieved great success in eliminating infectious diseases. Nevertheless, the epidemiological situation in the Union remains critical. Today, the death rate from infectious diseases ranks fourth after cardiovascular, neurological, and oncological diseases, besides, eliminated diseases have been replaced by new ones.

The purpose of the work: to identify the most dangerous infectious diseases that humanity has faced in recent years

Materials and methods: The study used official WHO data and reviews of epidemiological situations in the world

Results: Data analysis to do to us wide spread heavy transient and high death in the indicator infections the list to compose possibility gave They are from 35 between more than of a person to his life ground HIV infection millions people and to the global problem became Flu viruses (H1N1 (pig influenza) and H5N1 (poultry flu))

Too much dangerous contagious diseases - cholera , anthrax , plague , jaundice and hemorrhagic fever (Ebola, Lassa, Dengue , Zika and others) come in and this of diseases it's all a global community for serious risk gives birth Returned infections about that we don't forget need , they already defeated to be looks like One in line countries measles, poliomyelitis, diphtheria and malaria such as diseases the climax received This of diseases spread main reason of the population vaccination level low and prevention measures enough is not .

Conclusion . In the world epidemiological situation sharp , this while to the epidemic against measures done to increase the population between contagious to diseases against vaccination process to strengthen and at the borders sanitary quarantine control to strengthen demand does

Key words : epidemic , contagious diseases